

MIT ART, DESIGN AND TECHNOLOGY UNIVERSITY
MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

7th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON
RECENT TRENDS IN BIOENGINEERING
(ICRTB 2024)

January 19-20, 2024

ABSTRACTS

MIT School of
**Bioengineering Sciences
& Research**

Breathe Life into Engineering Career!

MIT-ADT
UNIVERSITY
PUNE, INDIA

A Leap Towards The World Class Education

PP-052

Multi-Omics Profiling of Lung Cancer for Identification of Precision Cancer Therapies

Nilofer Shaikh and Renu Vyas*

MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research, MIT Art, Design and Technology University, Rajbaugh Campus, Loni Kalbhor, Pune - 412201, Maharashtra, India.

Abstract: Lung cancer remains a formidable challenge in oncology, there is a need for a comprehensive understanding of the molecular landscape for the development of effective precision therapies. The high-throughput cancer-omics studies elucidate genomic, transcriptomic, proteomics, metabolomics and clinical data for the rapid discovery of potential biomarkers for early diagnosis. In the present study, the multi-omics data for lung cancer was extracted from the TCGA database of 5,329 cohort samples. Further by employing a Python package we identified 158 lung cancer driver genes based on mutation profiles against cohort samples and analyzed the presence of mutational signatures in genomic data. The driver genes were screened against precision oncology knowledge base data and annotated based on the biological consequences and clinical implications. Based on the level of clinical evidence 23 potential therapeutic and prognostic biomarkers were identified. The biomarkers were considered as a prioritization of candidate genes and further, the related oncogenic pathways with functional significance were identified. In conclusion, the survival analysis performed using Kaplan-Meier curves, and Cox proportional hazard models, we evaluated the impact of individual biomarker genes on patient survival outcomes. These multi-omics profiling of lung cancer provides a comprehensive framework for unravelling the complexities of the disease and identifying precise therapeutic targets. The insights gained from this study offer a roadmap for the development of precision and targeted interventions, marking a significant step towards improving outcomes in future studies.

Keywords: Multi-omics, Lung cancer, TCGA, Biomarker, Precision medicine

MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

Bioengineering is a multidisciplinary field that has gained immense importance in the global scenario. MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research is a constituent unit of MIT Art, Design and Technology University that aims to prepare students for ambitious careers in bioengineering by imparting education and hands-on training through project-based learning. The school helps in introducing students to the world of untapped opportunities in biology using engineering skills. The school envisions to empower India to become a leader in Bioengineering research, development and manufacturing sectors. It offers B. Tech. (Bioengineering), Int. M. Tech. (Bioengineering), M. Tech. (Environmental Bioengineering), M.Sc (Industrial Biotechnology) and Ph.D Programs in Biotechnology, Biomedical Engineering, Bioinformatics and Biomaterials. The super-specialized courses include Pharmaceutical Engineering, Synthetic Biology, Big Data Analytics, Biosensors and IoT, Biomedical Imaging, Biomechanics, Nano-Biotechnology, Robotics, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence, Environmental bioengineering, etc. The school is equipped with state-of-art laboratories for carrying out high-end research and innovative product development.

Rajbaug, Next to Hadapsar, Loni Kalbhor, Pune 412201, India.

+91 744 7444 027 / 28 | +91 914 6051 841 / 42

www.mitbio.edu.in / icrtb@mituniversity.edu.in

ISBN 978-93-6039-051-8

